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URL1: https://www.iscb.org/cms_addon/conferences/ismbeccb2021/tracks/gencompbio

URL2: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WDTNbfy3mJY>

URL3: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vARJ0ZiP7WY>

MoSwA: Protein Sequence Diversity Motif Switch Analyser for Viruses

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EXTENDED ABSTRACT

Protein sequence diversity is one of the major challenges in the design of diagnostic, prophylactic and therapeutic interventions against viruses. Shannon's entropy has been used as a quantitative measure of protein sequence diversity, applied via a user-defined k-mer sliding window [1, 2]. The entropy value of a given k-mer position in a sequence alignment is affected by the total number of distinct k-mer peptides observed at the position and their relative frequency, with a high entropy value indicating diversity, whereas an entropy of zero indicates complete conservation. Studies [3, 4] have classified distinct k-mer peptides at a given position into diversity motifs (index, major, minor, unique and k-mer_types) based on their incidence (*i.e.*, frequency). Index is the predominant sequence, and all others comprise as total variants, sub-classified into major variant (the predominant variant), minor variants (comprising of k-mers with incidence lower than major and higher than unique) and unique variants (k-mers seen only once in the alignment). These diversity motifs enable diversity dynamics analyses of virus proteins within and between species. Motif switching at a given k-mer alignment position is a phenomenon where fitness change in one or more amino acids, such as through mutations, changes the incidence of a given k-mer sequence across its overlapping positions, resulting in a sequence rank change, and thus, a motif change. This has been observed to occur for all the motifs (index, major, minor or unique). Identifying k-mer positions that exhibited a motif switch and determining the nature of the switches was a challenge given the large combination of switches that are possible and their omnipresence. Herein, we present MoSwA (Motif Switch Analyzer; <https://github.com/macelik/MoSwA>), a tool that not only identifies all alignment k-mer positions that exhibit motif switching, but also provides a multi-faceted and extensive characterisation of the switches. This includes:

- a short statistical summary on the switches observed;
- an alignment view of all the switches observed in a given dataset, referenced against a consensus sequence built from the index sequences of the k-mer positions;
- a network graph showing the dynamic interaction between the motif switches;

- a bar plot showing clusters of motif switch positions, as well as hotspots in the protein alignment;
- index switch positions are noteworthy and highlighted because highly conserved index at such positions are possibly to be avoided as vaccine targets given the instability of the index;
- a pairwise alignment score based on PAM30 is provided for index switches, to determine the physico-chemical spectrum of similarity/variability between the index sequence and the replacing variant motif sequence.

The input to MoSwA is a protein multiple sequence alignment. The user can choose to study a single, multiple or all diversity motifs. MoSwA now enables a comparative analyses of motif switches within and between viral species proteomes. This can help provide a better understanding of motif switches in relation to viral sequence diversity and evolution, with implications to vaccine and drug design.

(485 Words)

Figure 1: Selected features of MoSwA. A) A short statistical summary on the switches observed. B) A bar plot showing clusters of motif switch positions, as well as hotspots in the protein alignment. C) A network graph showing the dynamic interaction between the motif switches.

References: PMID: 18698358; 2. PMID: 19401763; 3. PMID: 32518710; 4. PMID: 23593157